

EXPRESSION OF HUMAN EXPERIENCES IN THE DRAMA "SOHIBQIRON"

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Annotation: *In this thesis, Abdulla Aripov's mastery of the expression of human emotions is once again described in his work "Sahibqiron".*

Keywords: *wife - spouse, Sultan ul-Arifin, Slave Ahmad - Ahmad Yassavi*

Abdulla Oripov is a well-known Uzbek poet and public figure. He is a well-known poet who sings deeply and honestly about the complexities and contradictions of the human heart in modern Uzbek poetry. Abdulla Aripov introduced a new way of thinking to modern Uzbek poetry. He wrote poems such as "Tilla Balykcha", "Why I Love Uzbekistan", and soon his first collection of poems "Little Star", followed by a number of rare works. He is also the author of our anthem. Each of the poet's works depicts the most delicate human emotions. For example, the drama "Sahibkiran" tells the story of Amir Temur. information about not only the palace, but also the daily activities of the owner is skillfully adapted to several scenes.

During the drama, Timur is portrayed in a whirlpool of thoughts, not on the battlefield.

As we read the work, we learn more about the personality of not only Sahibkiran, but also the people around him.

The first scene depicts Temur's aspirations for truth and justice, as well as the jealousy, enmity, ambition, and stinginess of his childhood friend Amir Hussein, as well as his sister Uljoy Turkon's love and devotion to Amir Temur.

It's as if Timur doesn't smile,

It's as if joy and happiness are alien to me. [1]

It is no exaggeration to say that these words, spoken in the language of Amir Temur, reflect his heart's desire for freedom and happiness.

The following verse from the play is a proof of the fact that Sahibkiran raised the flags of justice and religion in the country he founded:

Let everyone obey the law,

Let there be justice for all! [1]

Amir Hussein is a friend who grew up with Temur and is the brother of Uljoy Turkon. No matter how close he is to Sahibkiran, he lives with envy and jealousy towards Temur.

Your grandfather is not Chingiz, in fact he is jealous! [1]

Uljoy Turkon had a lot of respect and love for Sahibkiran. He says that he was heartbroken by the quarrel between his brother and his wife and asked for his brother's life from the Great Amir.

But when it falls to the ground, it is a worm-eaten fruit

A healthy root can not only preserve it [1]

From these words of the Great Amir, Uljoy Turkon said that he had a place in his life as a "healthy root", and Amir Hussein was an example of a "worm-eaten fruit", and now even a "healthy root" can not help him, the inevitability of punishment indicates. However, Amir Hussein asked Uljoy Temur for the poisoned bow he had prepared for Temur, and he committed suicide with it.

During the development of stage II, we describe the military skills of Amir Temur, his methods of governing the state, the battlefield, his mental state in the process. We can see how hard Sahibkiran was on the throne, how kind he was to his wives and family. His son Mironshah was sentenced to forty days in prison for assaulting his wife, Khonzodabegim. This story gives us the image of Timur as a just, kind, strict father.

We can see from the words of Bibi Khanum that he had to spend his life in battles, but in fact he also wanted to live in peace.

The innumerable destiny is with our wishes... [1]

Focusing on the fact that Amir Temur's grandchildren grew up educated and enlightened, in this 2nd scene he does not forget to check the military potential of his grandchildren during the negotiations on the battlefield styles. Because he says that the role of knowledge in the development of any country is invaluable:

And the prestige of any kingdom

With knowledge, with enlightenment. [1]

When he heard that his grandson Mirzo Ulugbek had beaten his teacher Aloviddin in a game of chess:

One day my generation will grow up

The conquerors of the earth will probably predict the future of their grandson by expressing the same opinion in science as in... [1].

Amir Temur's poem in a conversation with Hafiz Sherozi on stage III about the great respect for scholars and poets, as well as his creative work, is a clear example:

To listen to Haiz's poem in his own words,

I would conquer the land of Sheroz again. [1]

During his lifetime, Amir Temur often referred to the wisdom of Amad Yassavi. In scene , Amir Temur meets Hizr on his way to China and asks him to meet Sultan ul-Arif.

During his lifetime, Amir Temur often referred to the wisdom of Amad Yassavi. In scene V, Amir Temur meets Hizr on his way to China and asks him to meet Sultan ul-Arif and he achieves his goal. The slave gave his advice to Hodja Ahmad Sahibkiran and read about the nafs from the four. With the help of brief information about the drama "Sahibkiron" mentioned in the thesis, we can not only get acquainted with the personality of Amir Temur, but also directly praise the skill of Abdulla Aripov, because he gave such a perfect course of events, personal images, experiences. we feel as if we have fallen into that period, we "go inside" the work. Not only this work of the poet, but all the rest of his legacy will make us, the readers, excited to read.

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